

AUTOMATED NUCHAL CORD GRAPHICAL NEURAL NETWORK BASED FETAL ABNORMALITY PREDICTION

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Abstract—

By using classification algorithms, ultrasound medical imaging may readily detect fetal abnormalities by computing fetal parameters. An early diagnosis of fetal abnormalities allows the women to take the appropriate steps to protect her unborn child. In order to forecast fetal abnormalities using nuchal translucency, this study used a deep learning based nuchal cord graphical neural network. Here initially the Ultrasound images are retrieved and processed using Kalman transloop filter. Then the features are extracted using prolonged wrapper component analysis. Finally, the abnormality was detected using the nuchal cord graphical neural network. This research helps in the routine and continuous monitoring of fetal parameters of high-risk pregnant women. The article's findings suggest that the suggested techniques may help the least effective classifiers to provide reliable estimates of fetal abnormality risk.

Index Terms— Ultrasound, fetal abnormality, Kalman transloop filter, prolonged wrapper component analysis, nuchal cord graphical neural network

I. INTRODUCTION

A wide range of imaging modalities are at your disposal, including X-rays, nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR), CT scans, MRIs, and ultrasound systems. Since it is noninvasive, inexpensive, and poses no danger to the patient, brightness mode ultrasound—among others—is the most often used investigative technique [1]. In the United States, imaging using an external source is not necessary, but in most cases, injections of radio-opaque dyes are necessary in radiology [2]. Obstetricians and gynaecologists rely on organ imaging as their primary diagnostic tool [3]. When an appropriate beam of sound waves is sent via a transducer inside a human body, it shapes our perception of ourselves. Ultrasound pictures are produced by the duplication of received echo from interior organs. Further complicating segmentation assignment are picture creation features such as speckle, attenuation, missing borders, and artefacts [4].

There are about 11,000 abortions and 20,000 fatalities in India each year as a result of abortion-related complications, according to the National Consensus for Medical Abortion study [5]. In order to provide better healthcare for pregnant women, it is crucial to have accurate foetal parameter dimensions in US pictures. Important obstetrical indicators for foetal abnormalities identification include nuchal translucency thickness and foetal biometric measures. The gestational sac (G.Sac), biparietal diameter (BPD), head circumference (HC), abdominal circumference (AC), and femur length (FL) are the biometric markers that identify the foetus. The foetal gestational age and problems in growth may be detected using these biometric measures [1].

A foetal anomaly might be identified by measuring its nuchal translucency (NT) thickness between 11 and 14 weeks of gestation [6]. Accumulation of fluid in the nuchal region during the first trimester is referred to as NT thickness. Research has shown that an extra chromosome on chromosome 21 causes Down syndrome, a particular condition. On average, there are 23 sets of different chromosomes in each human cell. Each chromosome has genes that are beneficial for human development. A person acquires 23 chromosomes from both their mother and father at conception. Any parent might pass the extra chromosome on to their child. Research has recently shown that NT thickness measurements taken during the first trimester may detect foetal chromosomal abnormalities. The measurements taken using the population-based growth chart may identify both normal and aberrant growth. There is both inter- and intraobserver variability when foetal parameter assessments are done manually [7]. Measurements of foetal parameters taken automatically are more precise and repeatable, and they also decrease inconsistency [8, 9]. The use of automated foetal monitoring systems streamlines processes and allows for more precise measurements of foetal parameters. By accurately measuring these characteristics, the radiologist will be able to identify the foetal state [10].

From [11] to [17], we take a look at medical imaging and how it's processed, from acquiring the picture to enhancing it, segmenting it, compressing it, and finally storing it for future use in measuring anatomical and physiological data. Here in this work a novel nuchal cord graphical neural network was implemented for fetal abnormality prediction. The remainder of this work is broken down into the following sections: The second part is a review of related research. The paper's third portion focuses on the study's methodology. In the last chapter, the findings of the study are presented, examined, and discussed.

II. RELATED WORKS

“For foetal down screening, the project's prospective database was queried for NT measurements and detailed follow-up information [4]. The research did not include pregnancies that had structural or genetic abnormalities because the mothers had previous medical issues. We divided the pregnant women who tested positive for enhanced nuchal translucency (INT) (>95th%) into two groups: those whose INT was normal (<95th%) and those whose INT was elevated. The researchers in [5] looked at how well whole exome sequencing (WES) and chromosomal microarray analysis (CMA) worked with NT-rich foetuses. There were 374 singleton pregnancies included in the analysis, with gestational ages varying between 11 and 13 + 6 weeks. The work-enzyme-sequencing (WES) method is a laboratory-based approach to determining the nucleotide sequence, with a focus on the exonic regions and related sequences that comprise about 1% of the total DNA sequence. A comparison and study of convolutional neural learning approaches was conducted in [6]. Neural network detection of foetal anomalies made use of biometric features collected and assessed using segmentation techniques. A postpartum readmission strategy for mothers with hypertensive disorders of pregnancy was developed and tested using machine learning in [7]. Accurately predicting foetal weight at various stages of pregnancy without an ultrasound screening was the objective of the authors in [8]. Obstetricians may rely on machine learning for accurate forecasts, and pregnant women, in addition to conventional treatment choices, may benefit from a self-monitoring strategy that is both successful and efficient. The authors backed their claims with information gathered from 4,212 intrapartum observations. In [9], a number of AI-driven approaches to classifying foetal stages were detailed. Using a continuous cardiotocography (CTG) dataset, a multi-layer architecture of a sub-adaptive neuro fuzzy inference system (MLA-ANFIS) is used using neural networks (NN), deep stacked sparse auto-encoders (DSSAEs), and deep-ANFIS algorithms. All congenital abnormalities diagnosed after birth during 2006 and 2013 were compared to prenatal analyses of foetal malformations in 10,414 neonates and foetuses in [10]. Genomics sequencing (GS) (> 30-fold) was used in a retrospective research [11] for foetuses with an elevated NT (≥ 3.5 mm) who had routine prenatal testing. In order to determine the most effective method of defining an expanded nuchal translucency for the detection of unusual chromosomal abnormalities, the researchers in [12] set out to do a population-based, individual record linkage analysis. During the 35–36 week gestational period, 52,400 pregnant individuals who had a routine ultrasound were examined in the study [13]. Every pregnancy had an initial scan between 18 and 24 weeks, and 47,214 of them additionally had one between 11 and 13 weeks. All pregnancies that resulted in a healthy baby or mother's natural passing were considered, but those with congenital defects were not. We determined the kind and frequency of these abnormalities and classified them according to the affected major organ. The purpose of the study was to examine the results and therapeutic use of trio-based quick WES in the context of pregnancies with foetuses identified by ultrasonography as having a range of congenital abnormalities. More information regarding 55 foetuses was found in the study [15]. Inclusion criteria have included two or more separate serious foetal abnormalities, hydrops fetalis, or a serious foetal anomaly with a first-degree relative with a comparable disease. The scientists proposed a new architecture called SONO, which focuses on a convolutional neural network (CNN), to detect anatomical abnormalities and cardiac subgroups in foetal ultrasound recordings [16]. We used a timeline that looked like a barcode to assess and characterise the detection likelihood, and we got an anomaly score for every frame. Quick and accurate automated testing based on machine learning was crucial in evaluating bone fragments on computed tomography (CT) scanning in [17]. The time-consuming data collection and

interpretation make animal foetus micro-CT scan studies rare, despite their required in medication safety assessments.

III. PROPOSED WORK

As seen in Figure 1, the suggested technique uses ensemble machine learning techniques to categorise ultrasound images of foetal abnormalities. Ultrasound pictures of the foetus, b) image preprocessing and feature extraction, and c) image classification make up the whole approach.

Figure 1 Schematic representation of the suggested methodology

a. Fetal image dataset

Images of the foetus were retrieved by hand from Children's Hospital. A total of around 33 foetal ultrasound pictures were acquired and examined for any irregularities.

b. Data preprocessing

Improving US pictures is crucial for both computer-based and manual evaluation. A Kalman transloop filter was used in this case. Since US pictures are created using the pulse-echo method, it is difficult to distinguish between normal and pathological areas. The characteristic impedance of the medium is to be applied to the echoes received by the transducer:

$$I_{\text{reflect}} = I_{\text{incident}} \left[\frac{Z_1 - Z_2}{Z_1 + Z_2} \right]^2 \quad (1)$$

where Z_1 and Z_2 indicate the medium's typical impedance, I_{reflect} is the reflected ultrasound beam (echoes), and I_{incident} is the incident beam.

Ultrasound image contrast enhancement procedures are well-known. As a result of the object's acoustic statistics, the radiologist obtains US pictures with random fluctuations. Due to disturbances, it is difficult to distinguish microscopic and subtle structures. Due to the distributed nature of the backscattered echoes inside the tissue, speckle sounds are generated. Radiologists can miss the mark while dealing with speckle because of its existence. The use of US pictures in medical imaging is limited by the presence of speckle noise. Ultrasound image processing relies heavily on edge preservation and enhancement. After applying a number of statistical filters to the photos, the results are confirmed by the measurement of various parameters.

$$g(p, q) = f(p, q) - \text{median}_e(p, q) \quad (2)$$

where the predicted local contrast is denoted as $g(p, q)$. The picture grey level, denoted as $f(p, q)$, and the median grey level inside the area Q of (p, q) , as well as high-frequency noise, are produced by the native contrast. A high-pass transloop filter is analogous to Eq. (2).

c. Feature extraction

Substantiating linked variables into their component metrics is an essential part of the lengthy wrapper component analysis cycle. To improve the classification accuracy of fused feature (FF) vectors, principal component analysis (PCA) is used to decrease their dimensionality. While building the model, we took into account features that show how the data was correctly classified. The FF has n separate dimensions. The notion being considered in the initial $F = z_1, z_2, \dots, z_n$ contains several dimensions, thus it has to be reduced to the variable "kn." The protracted wrapper component analysis technique goes through a number of steps to get a set of fused features that have been reduced.

1. Data scaling:

$$O_j^i = \frac{o_j^i - \bar{o}_j}{\sigma_j} \quad (3)$$

2. Co-variance matrix computation:

$$\Sigma = \frac{1}{m} \sum_i^m (O_i)(O_i)^T, \Sigma \in R^{n \times n} \quad (4)$$

3. Third, we calculate the eigenvector and eigenvalue.:

$$V^T \Sigma = \lambda \mu U = \begin{bmatrix} | & | & | \\ V_1 & V_2 & \dots & V_n \\ | & | & | \end{bmatrix}, V_i \in R^n \quad (5)$$

4. Eigenvalue selection. The formula used in the selection process of the top 100 Eigenvalues in K-space for implementation into our classification system was as follows.

$$z_i^{\text{new}} = \begin{bmatrix} V_1^T z^i \\ V_2^T z^i \\ \dots \\ V_k^T z^i \end{bmatrix} \in R^k \quad (6)$$

5. At last the feature matrix was constructed.

d. Classification

The medical profession has widely employed the nuchal cord graphical neural network-based technique for diagnosis. During the diagnostic process, a variety of artificial intelligence methods are used to classify or find patterns in the raw data collected from patients. Here, the fetal NT thickness is the indicator of foetal abnormality detection. Fetal analysis relies on NT region characteristics that are retrieved from the spatial domain and transformed into the spatial domain in order to achieve the ideal goal of accurate NT of foetus measurement. In order to train these networks, a mapping between input and output data sets is performed. The generalized delta rule and algorithm learning are used to train this mapping by altering the weights. The proposed model involves classifying unknown input vectors after adjusting the NT weights on the training set until their value is stable. Minimizing the error term is specified as per the generalised delta rule.

$$E_K = 0.5 * \sum (t_k - y_k)^2 \quad (7)$$

In this equation, the index K represents the input vector, and t_k is the target vector and y_k are the actual output vectors.

$$\Delta w_{jk} = \eta \partial_k z_j \quad (8)$$

where η is the rate of learning, ∂_k is the local gradient, and Δw_{jk} is the change in weight from node j to k .

Finally, the thickness and the severity risk were identified.”

IV. PERFORMANCE ANALYSIS

The experimented evaluation of the suggested methodology was illustrated in in this section.

Figure 2 Sample input

Figure 3 Classification output

The severity classification was done on the sample input , from the analysis the severity of the fetal image was high as shown in figure 3.

To prove the efficiency of the suggested methodology it can be compared with the performance metrics like precision, accuracy, recall and F score.

Figure 4 Performance ratio of the suggested methodology

The performance ratio of the suggested methodology was illustrated in figure 4

Figure 5 Performance of AROC

Figure 5 shows the AROC performance, which is 0.9677, meaning the classifier does an excellent job of differentiating between the classes.

. Table 1 Performance analysis of various algorithms with the proposed method.

“Methods	Sensitivity	Matthews correlation coefficient	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-score
Machine learning algorithm (MLA) [18]	74.8	64.5	73.8	68.4	65.5	68.9
Feed forward neural network algorithm (FFNN) [18]	80.2	78.3	83.4	84.7	70.2	82.3
Ultrasound imaging techniques (UIT) [18]	68.4	70.9	71.2	72.4	74.6	74.6
Adaptive risk prediction system (ARPS) [18]	82.6	76.4	86.7	87.6	87.6	84.6
Proposed	99.8	99.7	99	98	99	99.2”

From the result obtained from table 1 it was revealed that the suggested methodology outperforms well by obtaining high range of the accuracy, precision, recall and f score.

V. CONCLUSION

An approach to NT identification and assessment based on deep learning was detailed in this study. The fundamental objective of this study was to develop and implement a novel method for the detection of NT fetal anomalies. This study used a new nuchal chord graphical network to detect NT fetal anomalies. The system as a whole gives very accurate NT detection results in both normal and pathological settings, as shown by quantitative and qualitative results. For individuals with abnormal umbilical arterial flow or congenital defects who do not need forced labor, the suggested model may help clinicians make judgements about pregnancies with fetal growth limitation. Sensitivity, maximum confidence interval, accuracy, precision, recall, and F1-score were used to evaluate the suggested method's performance. In comparison to the previous methods, the suggested model has a higher accuracy rate of 99%.

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